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Research Article

Formulation And Evaluation of a Novel Floating Pulsatile Delivery System of Nizatidine Tablets for Chronotherapeutic Release

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ABSTRACT

This study was conducted to develop floating pulsatile tablets of Nizatidine, a H₂ receptor antagonist, to release the drug as two distinct pulses separated by a lag time that achieve plasma concentration profiles varying in a circadian rhythm fashion, for the chronotherapy of ulcer. Floating pulsatile tablets were developed using two methods which differ in floating mechanism used. They are effervescence method and non-effervescence method (low density method). Effervescence method consisted of three different steps viz, preparation of floating sustained release drug containing tablets followed by time-lagged (4hrs) coating with hydrophobic rupturable polymer, ethyl cellulose (EC), and finally compression coating with immediate release dose of nizatidine and supporting buoyant layer. Three ratios of Ethyl cellulose to HPMC E15 (32.5:67.5, 50:50, and 67.5:32.5) at three coating levels (5%, 10%, 15%) were used to optimize the lag time (4hrs). Carbopol 934P, cross povidone and sodium bicarbonate were used in buoyant layer. The second method, low density method is similar to first method but gastro retention is based on low density system (glyceryl behenate wax-compritol 888) instead of effervescence. In this method core tablets were failed to float even after using several concentrations of compritol wax. Then time lagged coating was applied to these core tablets which also failed to float. So low density method was discontinued. The developed floating pulsatile tablets by effervescence method were evaluated for preformulation parameters, weight variation, thickness, hardness, friability, drug content, content uniformity, In vitro and In vivo floating properties, and In vitro drug release. The optimized formulation provided expected two-phase release pattern of Nizatidine with initial immediate dose release in 30 min and then lag time 4 hrs of no drug release followed by sustained release for 8hrs in stomach during floating. This approach suggested the use of floating pulsatile tablets as a promising drug delivery system for site and time specific release of Nizatidine acting as per chronotherapy of ulcer.

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INTRODUCTION

Gastrointestinal physiology and drug pharmacokinetics follow circadian rhythms, influencing both disease manifestation and therapeutic response. The circadian clock, governed by the suprachiasmatic nuclei of the hypothalamus, regulates numerous biological processes such as sleep wake cycles, hormone secretion, and gastric acid production [1]. Conditions like peptic ulcers and gastroesophageal reflux disease (GERD) exhibit nocturnal exacerbations of acidity, typically between midnight and early morning hours [2,3]. Hence, chronotherapeutics the alignment of drug release with biological rhythms has become a promising approach for enhancing efficacy and minimizing side effects [4,5].

Nizatidine is a selective histamine H₂ receptor antagonist indicated for the treatment of gastric and duodenal ulcers. It exhibits a short half-life (1–2 hours) and undergoes extensive first-pass metabolism, necessitating multiple daily doses for effective acid suppression [6,7]. However, conventional formulations fail to maintain therapeutic levels during the nocturnal acid breakthrough phase, leading to incomplete acid control [8].

To address this limitation, floating pulsatile drug delivery systems (FPDDS) have been developed. These systems combine gastro-retentive mechanisms with time-controlled drug release, ensuring the release of drug at a predetermined lag time after ingestion [9]. Floating systems remain buoyant in the gastric environment due to gas generation (effervescent) or low-density matrices (non-effervescent) [10].

In the present study, Nizatidine floating pulsatile tablets were formulated to synchronize drug release with circadian patterns of gastric acid

secretion. The effervescent method utilized sodium bicarbonate as the gas-generating agent and HPMC as a swellable matrix to achieve buoyancy. The rupturable coating composed of ethyl cellulose and HPMC E15 controlled the lag phase before the second pulse of release [11]. The non-effervescent (low-density) method using Compritol 888 wax was explored but found unsuitable due to inadequate floating behavior.

This innovative dual-mechanism approach aimed to achieve:

1. Immediate drug release for postprandial acid suppression,
2. A programmed lag phase (≈ 4 hours), and
3. A subsequent sustained-release pulse maintaining therapeutic levels during nocturnal periods.
4. Such a system offers improved chronotherapeutic management of ulcers, reduces dosing frequency, and enhances patient compliance [12,13].

2. MATERIALS AND METHODS

2.1 MATERIALS

Nizatidine was received as a sample from Natco Pharma Ltd., Hyderabad. Excipients included HPMC K4M, HPMC E15, ethyl cellulose (EC, 50 cps), Carbopol 934P, crosspovidone, sodium bicarbonate, magnesium stearate, talc, lactose, dibutyl phthalate, and Compritol 888 (glyceryl behenate) obtained from reputed pharmaceutical suppliers [7,10]. All solvents were of analytical grade and used as received.

2.1.1 Equipment

1. Formulation and evaluation were performed using:

2. Tablet compression machine (Rimek Minipress II)

3. Pharma R&D coater (VJ Instruments Ltd.)

4. UV spectrophotometer (Lab India UV-3000 Plus)

5. USP Dissolution Apparatus II (Lab India DS-8000)

6. FT-IR Spectrophotometer (Shimadzu)

7. Differential Scanning Calorimeter (Perkin Elmer)

8. Hardness tester (Monsanto) and Roche Friabilator.

All instruments were calibrated before use.

2.2 Methods

2.2.1 Determination Of Amax And Calibration Curve

A stock solution of Nizatidine (1000 µg/mL) was prepared in 0.1 N HCl. Absorbance was measured at 314 nm using UV-VIS spectrophotometer, and a standard calibration curve (50–250 µg/mL) was plotted [8].

2.2.2 Formulation of Floating Pulsatile Tablets

2.2.2.1 Effervescence Method

This approach involved three sequential steps:

Step 1 – Preparation of Floating Core Tablets:

Nizatidine and HPMC K4M were mixed in ratios of 1:1, 1:1.5, and 1:2 with sodium bicarbonate (10% w/w) as effervescent agent. The blends were

lubricated with magnesium stearate and talc and compressed using 9 mm punches (Rimek Minipress II). Each tablet contained 75 mg of Nizatidine.

Step 2 – Time-Lagged Coating:

Coating dispersion (8% w/w) containing ethyl cellulose and HPMC E15 in weight ratios of 37.5:62.5, 50:50, and 67.5:32.5 was prepared using isopropyl alcohol and water. Dibutyl phthalate (20% w/w) and talc (5% w/w) were added as plasticizer and glidant. Tablets were coated in a Pharma R&D coater to weight gains of 5%, 10%, and 15%, followed by drying at 40°C for 2 hours.

Step 3 – Compression Coating:

An immediate-release layer comprising Nizatidine (75 mg), Carbopol 934P, crosspovidone, sodium bicarbonate, and lactose was used to compression-coat the optimized core tablets. Crosspovidone enhanced rapid disintegration for the first pulse release, while sodium bicarbonate ensured buoyancy [12,13].

2.2.2.2 Non-Effervescence (Low-Density) Method

In this method, Compritol 888 (glyceryl behenate) was used as a low-density matrix former. Direct compression was employed, but tablets failed to float due to inadequate buoyancy; hence, this approach was discontinued [10].

2.2.3 Evaluation Parameters

Preformulation Studies: FT-IR and DSC confirmed absence of drug–excipient interaction.

Post-Compression Evaluation: Tablets were assessed for weight variation, hardness, friability, thickness, and drug content as per USP guidelines.

Buoyancy Studies: Conducted in 0.1 N HCl (pH 1.2, $37 \pm 0.5^\circ\text{C}$) to determine floating lag time and total floating duration.

In Vitro Dissolution Studies: Using USP Apparatus II at 100 rpm in 900 mL of 0.1 N HCl, samples were withdrawn at predetermined intervals and analyzed spectrophotometrically at 314 nm.

Kinetic Modelling: Release data were fitted to zero-order, first-order, Higuchi, and Korsmeyer–Peppas models. The optimized formulation (CCF3) followed Higuchi diffusion-controlled zero-order kinetics [9-13].

2.2.4 Statistical and Stability Evaluation

All experiments were conducted in triplicate ($n = 3$) and results expressed as mean \pm SD. Stability testing was performed for 60 days at $40^\circ\text{C} \pm 2^\circ\text{C}/75\% \pm 5\% \text{RH}$ per ICH Q1A(R2) guidelines [12].

3. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

3.1 Determination of Lambda Max of Nizatidine:

After scanning 10 $\mu\text{g}/\text{ml}$ solution of Nizatidine the lambda max of Nizatidine was found to be 314nm (absorbance-0.106).

Fig.no.1: Spectrum of Nizatidine 10 $\mu\text{g}/\text{ml}$ Solution in 0.1n HCL

3.2 Standard Graph of Nizatidine In 0.1N HCL:

The scanning of the volumetric solution of Nizatidine in the ultraviolet range (200- 400nm) against 0.1 N HCl blank gave the λ_{max} as 314 nm.

The standard concentrations of Nizatidine (50-250 $\mu\text{g}/\text{ml}$) prepared in 0.1N HCl showed good linearity with R2 value of 0.998, which suggests that it obeys the Beer-Lamberts law

Table no.1.: Observations for calibration curve of Nizatidine in 0.1 N HCL

Concentration ($\mu\text{g}/\text{mL}$)	Absorbance				Standard Deviation (SD)
	1	2	3	Average*	
0	0	0	0	0	0
50	0.208	0.211	0.235	0.218	0.0148
100	0.391	0.400	0.408	0.399	0.0085
150	0.558	0.590	0.591	0.579	0.0187
200	0.752	0.803	0.803	0.786	0.029
250	0.955	0.974	0.979	0.969	0.012

Fig.no.2: Standard graph of Nizatidine in 0.1N HCl

3.3drug-Excipient Interaction Studies:

3.3.1 Fourier Transform Infrared Spectroscopic Studies (FTIR)

The FTIR spectra of drug and optimised formulation were recorded. The characteristic peaks of the optimized formulation followed the same trajectory as that of the drug alone with minor differences. Thus there may be no drug-excipient interactions.

Fig.no.3: FTIR spectra of Nizatidine pure drug

Fig.no.4: FTIR spectra of optimised formulation (CCF3)

Table no.2.: FTIR peak positions(cm^{-1}) and assignments for Nizatidine and its optimised formulation (CCF3)

Nizatidinedrug	Optimisedformulation(CCF3)	Frequency range	Modeofvibration
2941.44	2939.52	2950-2800	CH
1469.76	1469.76	1454-1475	CH ₂
2827.64	2827.64	2850-2815	CH ₃
1469.75	1469.75	1475	C=C
1261.45	1261.45	1360-1250	C-N
3278.99	3278.99	3500-3180	N-H
1375.25	1377.17	1380-1360	NO ₂
	3404.36	3400-3300	OH
	2351.23	2800-2340	OH
	1072.42	1260-1000	CO
	1058.92	1300-1000	C-O-C

3.3.2 Differential Scanning Calorimetric Study (DSC):

DSC study was conducted for Nizatidine and optimised formulation (CCF3). DSC thermogram of pure Nizatidine shows sharp exothermic peak at 138.4°C. Similar exothermic peak was obtained at 136°C for the optimised formulation.

Table no.3.: DSC melting points of the selected formulations

Formulations	DSC meltingpointin°C
PureNizatidines	138.4
Nizatidine+HPMCK4M+K15M	136

Fig.no.5: DSC thermogram of pure drug Nizatidine

Fig.no.6: DSC thermogram of optimised formulation

3.4 Flow Properties of Floating Core and Compression Coated Tablet Blends:

The powder blends of floating tablets (F1-F3) and compression coated tablets were evaluated for their flow properties, the results were shown in Table 24. Angle of repose was in the range from 21.8 to 28.14 which indicates good flow of the powder for all formulations. The values of bulk

density were found to be in the range from 0.51 to 0.623 gm/cc; the tapped density was in the range of 0.597 to 0.684 gm/cc. The Carr's index was found to be in the range from 11.10 to 17.25. The Hausner ratio was found to be in the range from 1.16 to 1.37. These results indicate that the powdered blends exhibited good flow properties and have good compressibility.

Table no.4.: Results of flow properties of core and compression coated tablet blends:

Formulation code	Angle of repose (°)	Bulk density(gm/cc)	Tapped density(gm/cc)	Carr's Index (%)	Hausner ratio
F1	28.14	0.561	0.652	13.95	1.16
F2	26.89	0.542	0.655	27.25	1.20
F3	24.22	0.514	0.598	14.71	1.17
CCF1	23.14	0.623	0.684	17.36	1.15
CCF2	25.23	0.610	0.624	19.25	1.25
CCF3	26.45	0.596	0.634	18.34	1.37

3.5 Post Compression Parameters of Floatingcoreand Compression Coated Tablets of Nizatidine:

The final tablets were white, smooth, and flat, round shaped in appearance. The thickness was measured by vernier calipers and was ranged between 4 ± 0.20 and 4.1 ± 0.09 mm. The diameter was measured and ranged between 11.04 ± 0.11 to 11.12 ± 0.11 mm. The weight variation for different formulations (F1 to F3) showed

satisfactory results as per United States Pharmacopoeia (USP) limit (average weight $\pm 5\%$). The hardness was measured by Monsanto tester and was found to be ranged from 4.66 ± 0.28 to 5.16 ± 0.28 kg/cm². The friability was found to be ranged from 0.472 to 0.76 which was below 1% indicating good mechanical resistance of the tablets. The percentage of drug content for all formulations was found to be in between 98.1 ± 1.21 to 103.03 ± 0.45 of Nizatidine, it complies with official specifications (95 to 110%).

Table no.5.: Results of Post Compression Properties core and compression coated tablets of Nizatidine

Formulation Code	Thickness (mm)	Diameter (mm)	Hardness (kg/cm ²)	Friability (%)	Drug content(%)	Weight variation(%)
F1	3.90±0.05	8.9±0.09	4.76±0.25	0.503	99.89±1.75	4.1%
F2	3.85±0.03	8.9±0.1	5.23±0.25	0.543	99.93±2.71	3.5%
F3	3.89±0.04	8.8±0.15	5.16±0.28	0.488	102.63±2.1	2.8%
CCF1	4.10±0.02	12.01±0.12	5.12±0.29	0.622	98.33±2.41	4.6%
CCF2	4.12±0.04	11.95±0.16	5.24±0.35	0.569	101.22±1.25	3.9%
CCF3	4.09±0.01	12.18±0.24	5.36±0.22	0.658	99.56±1.42	2.2%

3.6 In Vitro Buoyancy Studiescore and Compression Coated Tablets of Nizatidine:

All the tablets were prepared by effervescent approach. The results of floating study were shown in table 27. On immersion in 0.1N HCL solution pH (1.2) at 37°C, the tablets floated, and remained buoyant without disintegration. Sodium bicarbonate was used as the effervescent base. When the floating matrix tablets containing gas generating agent were exposed to 0.1N HCl, hydrochloric acid reacted with sodium bicarbonate in the floating tablet inducing CO₂ formation. The generated gas was entrapped into the matrix of swollen polymer matrix and was well protected by gel formed by hydration of polymers, which led to floating of the dosage forms.

Table no.6.: Results of In vitro Buoyancy study

Formulation code	Buoyancy Lag Time (SEC)	Total Floating Time (HRS)
F1	120	>5
F2	154	>6
F3	180	>7
CCF1	256	>12
CCF2	189	>12
CCF3	129	>12

In core tablet formulations as the HPMC K4M level increasing the FLT increased. As the polymer concentration increases it takes more time for the polymer matrix to hydrate and swell and then float, so FLT increased. In compression coated formulations, FLT decreased in the order CCF1>CCF2>CCF3. This is due to addition of cross povidone to CCF2 and CCF3 which has higher swelling index than carbopol and helps in floating along with carbopol. So floating lag time decreased.

3.7 In Vitro Dissolution Studies Of Core, Spray Coated, And Compression Coated Tablets Of Nizatidine:

In vitro dissolution studies of all the formulations of Nizatidine were carried out in 0.1 N HCl and percentage drug release was calculated.

No. 7 Table. Results of In vitro dissolution studies of Nizatidine floating core tablets

Time(min)	F1	F2	F3
0	0	0	0
60	44.4±0.88	41.7±0.6	35.4±0.57
120	54.55±0.96	49.43±0.73	44.6±0.72
180	71.35±0.83	59.31±0.87	58.04±0.82
240	85.84±0.88	77.63±1.1	69.76±0.75
300	97.11±0.6	85.56±0.87	81.85±0.9
360		98.49±0.95	89.09±0.92
420			98.39±0.57

Fig.no.7: DSC thermogram of optimised formulation

By increasing the amount of HPMC K4M the drug release was decreased proportionately in the following order $F1 < F2 < F3$. Among these formulations F3 was selected for further

development as it has sustained the release of Nizatidine up to 7hrs which is near to the desired release profile (8hrs).

Table no.8.: Results of In vitro dissolution studies of Nizatidine floating core tablets spray coating (CF1-CF9)

Time(min)	CF1	CF2	CF3	CF4
0	0	0	0	0
60	13.50±0.54	6.00±1.04	3.00±0.68	2.40±0.6
120	25.28±0.93	12.03±0.95	7.52±0.72	6.61±0.84
180	32.32±0.82	19.90±0.8	16.56±0.76	14.75±1.03
240	37.29±1.03	23.91±0.83	23.55±0.82	25.93±0.88
300	45.30±0.6	31.54±0.91	29.68±0.79	35.08±0.87
360	49.45±0.86	43.12±0.96	41.84±0.98	41.27±0.99
420	59.45±0.9	52.57±0.71	49.81±0.89	51.31±0.97
480	68.94±0.96	63.79±0.90	58.85±0.92	59.48±1
540	81.62±0.75	74.89±0.81	66.37±0.67	65.80±0.78
600	87.46±0.97	84.90±0.86	74.23±0.68	75.76±0.65
660	97.54±0.69	94.06±0.87	86.94±1.01	84.87±0.81

Time(min)	CF5	CF6	CF7	CF8	CF9
0	0	0	0	0	0
60	1.8±0.8	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00
120	5.71±0.88	4.80±0.96	2.70±1.52	0.30±2.38	0.30±2.38
180	10.54±1.7	9.33±2	6.32±2.97	3.60±0.98	3.61±0.98
240	16.00±1.21	12.68±1.76	11.45±2.15	10.52±2.48	4.83±0.89
300	24.79±1.41	17.25±1.12	13.91±2.07	20.48±1.35	20.45±1.34
360	30.93±0.6	22.74±12.98	20.59±0.58	30.79±0.95	28.37±1.49
420	38.91±1.06	30.46±1.4	28.32±1.64	40.89±2.48	40.86±2.47
480	46.61±1.11	37.44±1.47	41.26±2.01	55.19±2.22	53.05±0.88
540	52.27±0.88	42.74±0.86	54.69±1.01	65.39±0.92	69.54±1.79
600	69.65±2.29	49.88±1.28	72.69±1.09	78.95±2.93	84.02±1.72

660	75.13±2.22	62.45±2.27	87.19±1.03	92.28±2.21	98.27±3.73
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The amount of ethyl cellulose was increased from CF1 to CF9. The increase in lag time from CF1 to CF9 was due to decreased permeability and increased hydrophobicity of coating membrane because of the increasing concentration of insoluble polymer (ethyl cellulose-37.5- 50-62.5) as well as increased coating thickness (5-10-15%). Both the factors (weight ratio of polymers

and coating thickness) have antagonistic effect on total drug release with drug release decreasing on elevating the level of either of the factors. However the effect of weight ratio of ethyl cellulose to HPMC seems to be more pronounced as compared with that of coating level. Release rate decrease was also due to more tortuous diffusional path length due to increase in coating thickness.

Fig.no.8: Comparative drug release profiles of Nizatidine floating pulsatile tablets (CF1- CF9)

Table no.9.: Results of In vitro drug release of Nizatidine floating pulsatile tablets with immediate release dose-compression coating (CCF1-CCF3)

Time(min)	CCF1	CCF2	CCF3
0	0	0	0
30	64.5±0.98	82.5±2.2	99.00±2.03

60	82.56±1.12	99.16±3.29	1.45±2.64
120	98.32±1.66	2.40±1.56	2.45±1.56
180	4.81±0.88	4.51±0.94	3.61±1.17
240	6.04±1.15	6.34±1.12	4.53±1.44
300	21.37±1.63	22.87±1.34	21.96±1.49
360	29.74±2.04	31.54±1.45	31.24±1.55
420	44.16±1.35	47.78±1.81	45.05±1.33

480	56.61±1.28	59.25±1.65	55.46±1.38
540	72.31±2.53	75.36±2.08	72.90±2.4
600	79.00±1.7	80.57±1.38	80.80±1.35
660	86.93±0.6	89.41±1.13	89.35±1.11
720	97.01±0.81	98.60±0.84	99.43±1.04

In CCF only Carbopol was used. The floating lag time and floating time were good for CCF1 but took two hours to release the immediate release dose of Nizatidine. So to enhance fast release of

immediate dose the super disintegrant, cross povidone was added in CCF2(5mg), CCF3(10mg). Target release of immediate dose within 30min was achieved with CCF3 followed by lag time up to fourth hour and sustained release up to 8hrs. Cross povidone worked both to enhance the release of Nizatidine immediately and also decreased the floating lag time due to its instant high swelling.

Fig.no.9: Comparative drug release profiles of Nizatidine floating pulsatile tablets with immediate release dose-compression coating.

Fig.no.10: Kinetic release plots of optimised floating core tablet (F3) - Zero order, First order

3.8 Kinetic Modelling of Drug Release from Nizatidine Floating Core Tablets:

Kinetics were applied only to floating core tablets(matrix) because there is no drug release for certain time in floating pulsatile tablets. The in

in vitro dissolution data were fitted in different kinetic models viz. zero order, first order, Higuchi and Korsmeyer-Peppas equation. Correlation coefficients of all formulations showed higher correlation with zero order plots than first order. So, predominant drug release order is controlled release. To confirm the exact mechanism of drug release from these tablets, the data were fitted to Higuchi and Korsmeyer-Peppas equation. All

three formulations showed higher regression values for Higuchi model indicating the release mechanism was Higuchi matrix diffusion. The causes for diffusion may be due to the swollen insoluble hydrogel matrix, which entrapped the drug. According to Peppas kinetics based on n value the mechanism of drug release for F1, F2 was Fickian diffusion and F3 was non Fickian or anomalous transport.

Fig.no.11: Kinetic release plots of optimised floating core tablet (F3) - Zero order, First order

Fig.no.12: Kinetic release plots of optimised floating core tablet (F3)- Higuchi, peppas model

Table no.10.: Results of Kinetic Modelling of Nizatidine Floating Core Tablets

Formulation code	Zero order	First order	Higuchi	Peppas	Peppas
	2 R	2 R	2 R	2 R	n
F1	0.994	0.878	0.978	0.97	0.498

4. CONCLUSION

The present study demonstrates that Nizatidine could be successfully delivered to provide relief of gastric acidity in the mid night (nocturnal acid breakthrough) and in the afternoon by design of a floating pulsatile chronopharmaceutical formulation. The formulation is to be taken after meal, where immediate release dose will provide relief from acid secretion in response to the meal, while timed pulsatile release floating tablet with delayed “sustained” release will attenuate midnight and afternoon acidity. This will provide an ideal therapeutic regimen with enhanced patient compliance in the chronotherapy of ulcer. Three ratios at three levels were used in the development of time-lagged coating formulations based on rupturable (ethyl cellulose) and erodible (hydroxypropyl methylcellulose) polymers to achieve the desired pulsed release profile after a programmed lag time. The effect of weight ratio of ethyl cellulose to HPMC seems to be more pronounced as compared with that of coating level. The coating formulation containing ethyl cellulose and hydroxypropyl methyl cellulose in percentage weight ratio of 67.75:37.25 at 15% coating level (CF9) has showed desired lag time (4 hrs) followed by sustained release that has the potential for time-controlled pulsatile delivery of Nizatidine. The final optimized formulation from compression coating (CCF3) exhibited release profiles which were close to the set targets (immediate dose release-30min, lag time- 3.30hrs, sustained release-8hrs). This work can be extended for time scheduled release of drugs having high

solubility, and poor absorption or enzymatic degradation in the colon. Thus the designed formulation can be considered as one of the promising formulation technique for preparing floating pulsatile drug delivery systems and hence in chronotherapeutic management of ulcer by opening a “new therapeutic dimension” to an existing drug molecule.

5. Conflict Of Interest Statement

We declare that we have no conflict of interest.

6. ACKNOWLEDGMENTS

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